

A METHOD TO MEASURE WETTING BETWEEN RESIN AND REINFORCEMENT

L. Magnus Dahlbäck and T. Staffan Lundström
Swedish Institute of Composites
Box 271
94126 Piteå
Sweden

ABSTRACT

A new method to measure wetting between resin and reinforcement in polymer composites is studied. The method measures contact angle, height and width of a drop applied on a porous surface which in this case is fibre bundles. Several material combinations are tested including epoxy, vinyl ester, glass and carbon fibres. For four pairs of material combinations the properties of the manufactured composites are known. In three of these cases poor wetting was followed by lower than expected properties of the composite. The overall conclusion is that the equipment can be used as a tool for selection of optimum material combinations.

1. INTRODUCTION

A significant area in production of Fibre Reinforced Polymer Composites (FRPC) is wetting between the polymer and the fibres. An improvement of the wettability will result in easier production and improved quality of the product. One main advantage with FRPC is that different material combinations can be used to suit the application of the composite. In this choice wetting between the components is one important parameter. Hence a reliable method to measure wettability is necessary.

The fibres used in FRPC are often gathered in bundles, which can contain hundreds or even thousands of fibres. These bundles are sometimes assembled forming fibre mats. When measuring the wetting compatibility it is not clear whether the wetting shall be measured on the single fibres, the fibre bundles or the fibre mats. Even though measurements on single fibres, e.g. Wilhelmy method, the Liquid membrane method and the method of Spreading of liquid droplets on cylindrical surfaces [1-3], at a first glance seem to be the most proper way to measure wettability, several factors may influence the choice. Uneven distribution of surface treatment on single fibres can give large deviation of the wetting measurement on individual fibres. Single fibre measurements are not suitable when the fibres bundles have been treated with coating or when the fibre mats are applied with binder. For several processes of FRPC the fibres are not wetted individually. Instead, a number of fibres are wetted simultaneously. Hence, measurements on single fibres do not always give a value of the wetting relevant to actual conditions in production of FRPC. Methods to measure wetting on fibre bundles and

fibre mats have also been presented, the Wicking method [4] and the method of Wet-out time [5]. The main drawbacks with the wicking method is that large channels between the fibre bundles can influence the wicking. For the Wet-out time method the reinforcement geometry may strongly influence the results. Therefore, there is a need for a complementary method to measure the compatibility between polymers and fibre mats or fibre bundles. With the device FIBRO 1100 DAT, it is possible to dynamically measure the contact angle, the height and the base of a drop are applied to a porous media such as fibremats or fibre bundles.

The purpose of this work is to experimentally develop and justify whether the FIBRO 1100 DAT is a good way to measure the wetting of fibre composites or not. Parameters like fibre diameter, type of sizing and tex number are varied to test the sensibility of the equipment. The DAT is also tested on four material combinations that are known to exhibit different mechanical properties or variation in void content. These cases are: 1) Vinylester/epoxy and carbonfibre mat, 2) Vinylester and glassfibre mat with and without sizing, 3) Vinylester and S-glass/E-glassfibre mat and 4) Epoxy and glassfibre bundles with different surface treatment.

2. BACKGROUND

Wetting is popularly used as an expression for how well a liquid spreads on a surface. For example a water drop on a properly waxed car roof usually shows bad wetting, while water drops on a clean glass window wets very well. Wetting is sometimes also used as an expression for how well a porous medium such as a piece of cotton-wool absorbs liquid by capillary action. In this report this effect will be called absorption. Physically, wetting depends on inter-atomic and intermolecular forces of attraction between liquid and solid and is commonly characterised by the value of the contact angle. The contact angle describes the shape of the liquid in a mechanical equilibrium position. This was first studied by Young [6], who connected the surface energies by:

$$\gamma_{SV} = \gamma_{SL} + \gamma_{LV} \cos \theta \quad (1)$$

where γ_{SV} , γ_{SL} and γ_{LV} are the surface free energies of the solid-vapour, solid-liquid and liquid-vapour interfaces, respectively, and θ is the static contact angle.

When a liquid drop is put into contact with a porous medium, it may both spread on the surface by wetting and penetrate into the medium by absorption, see Fig. 1. Absorption, which is a consequence of wetting, is mostly the result of capillary action in the pores of the porous medium. The capillary pressure is set by the capillary structure and the surface energies and can be expressed as follows for a tube with circular cross-section:

$$P_c = \frac{4\gamma_{LV} \cos \theta}{D_c} \quad (2)$$

where D_e is the equivalent hydraulic channel diameter.

Fig. 1. Typical development of a liquid drop wetting a porous media.

Fig. 2. Typical contact angle as a function of time for a drop wetting a porous and solid media.

When the liquid wets the capillaries it will penetrate into the porous media and the contact angle of the drop will change in time, see Figure 2. By assuming constant change in θ by the absorption the static value of θ can be approximated also for the porous media.

3. EXPERIMENTAL EQUIPMENT AND MATERIALS

The material used in the experiment are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Resins and fibres used in the experimental work. The viscosity was measurement with a Bohlin Visco 88 BV viscometer.

Resin/fibre type	Viscosity mPas (T=25°C)/ Geometrical type
CIBA-GEIGY Araldite LY556/HY917 (epoxy)	610
DOW Derakane 8084 (vinylester)	620
Ahlström R338 (E-glassfibre)	Fibre bundle
Reference fibre RA (E-glassfibre)	Fibre bundle
Brochier Lyvertex 21130 (E-glassfibre)	Woven mat
Brochier Injectex GU230 (carbon)	Woven mat
Hexcel 4543 (S-glassfibre)	Woven mat
RPA 38 STC (E-glassfibre)	Fibre bundle
158 B30 (E-glassfibre)	Fibre bundle

The FIBRO 1100 Dynamic Adsorption Tester (DAT), Fig 3, was used to measure the contact angle, drop height and drop width of a liquid drop with very short intervals (20 milliseconds). The measuring device contains an electronically controlled medical pump, a CCD camera and a

position controlling mechanism for the specimen. The procedure was as follows: The fibre bundles were taped parallel, close to each other, so that the edge effect of each fibre bundle was eliminated. The fibre-mats were taped in the same way as the fibre bundles except for that the mats needed a frame of tape, to prevent single fibres to protrude up from the surface. The volume of the drop was selected to 5 μl , which gives a radius of 1 mm for the spherical shaped drop. The drop was automatically applied to the surface of the specimen and video images of the drop were captured until the drop was totally absorbed. Then the sample was advanced to a new position and a new drop was applied. The captured images were evaluated by image analysis to give values of the height, width and contact angle of the liquid drop as a function of time. The values of five drops were averaged and used to calculate the standard deviation to give a view of the spreading of the results. The experiments were performed at 23°C.

Figure 3: Sketch of the FIBRO 1100 DAT equipment.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

As stated in the previous section the DAT gives geometrical data for the drops. Here the contact angle will be presented since it gives a good representation of the results but curves of the other parameters can be obtained from [7]. The materials used are specified in the previous section.

Variation of tex number (300 to 900 g/km) fibre diameter (14 to 19 mm), amount of sizing (0.5-0.7 %) on Ahlström fibre bundles did not lead to any noticeable difference in wetting behaviour. However testing two types of surface treatment gave large deviations, see Fig. 4. Fibre bundle 338 shows, much better wetting qualities than the reference fibre bundle RA although the fibre bundles have similar fibre radius and the same tex-number. The static contact angle is approximately 25° for R338, but around 55° for RA and the first part of the curve is much steeper for R338 than for RA.

Fig. 4. Contact angle versus time for epoxy on fibre bundles with different sizing. ♦ reference RA, ◇ Ahlström R338. The points are average of five measurements and the bars denotes the standard deviation.

The materials used in the following experiments have previously been tested for mechanical performance and void content and their qualities will later on be compared with their wetting properties. The cases are: 1) Vinylester/epoxy and carbonfibre mat, 2) Vinylester and glassfibre mat with and without sizing, 3) Vinylester and S-glass/E-glassfibre mat and 4) Epoxy and glassfibre bundles with different surface treatment.

The results on the wettability are presented in Fig. 5 to 8. For the first case the epoxy has a lower static contact angle than the vinylester and continues to wet the fibres better than the vinylester resin. The epoxy spreads out and absorbs into the reinforcement while the vinylester moves into a static state early in the wetting process although the viscosity of the resins are similar, see Table 1. One reason for this can be that epoxy is more attracted to organic materials than the vinylester.

Figure 5. Contact angle in time for epoxy (♦) and vinylester (◇) applied on a carbon fibre weave.

For the second case, Fig. 6, an E-glassfibre mat is burned in an oven for 5 hours at 556°C and then compared to an unburned fibre mat. The burned fibre mat shows better wetting qualities. One explanation is the sizing dependency on the surface energy another is that when the fibres are burned the fibre bundles get looser and may be easier to impregnate.

Fig. 6. Contact angle versus time for vinyl ester applied to the E-glassfibre mats. One is burned, ◆ and the other is unmodified, ◇.

For the third case, the wettability of S-glassfibre mats and E-glassfibre mats with vinyl ester are compared, Fig.7. The S-glass gives higher values of the contact angle than the E-glass. There is an approximate difference of 20° for the static contact angle. Probably it is not the difference in glass type that makes the difference in wettability. It is rather the type of sizing on the reinforcement. The geometry of the reinforcement can also have a major role. However both these fibre mats are very compact and highly unidirectional.

Fig. 7. Contact angle versus time for vinyl ester on E- and S-glassfibre mats. ◆ E-glass, ◇ S-glass.

Finally for the fourth case, two types of fibre bundles are compared regarding their wettability qualities with an epoxy resin, Fig. 8. There is no clear difference between the contact angles.

Fig. 8. Contact angle versus time for epoxy applied on fibre bundles with different sizing. ◆ RPA 38 STC, ◇ 158 B30.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Several experiments with the DAT have been presented. For some cases no differences in wettability was observed while for other cases significant differences in wettability were obtain with small variations of the components. Poor wettability may lead to formation of voids and bad chemical binding resulting in poor mechanical properties. Therefore four cases were studied with known properties of the composite.

Regarding case one the vinylester/carbonfibre have previously shown on unexpected bad mechanical properties. The wetting properties is also worse for this combination compared with the epoxy/carbonfibre combination, Fig. 5. Also mechanical test on the vinylester/S-glass combination have given lower strength than expected. As for case one this follows the wetting behaviour of the components, Fig 7.

For composites with the materials in case two the void content has been measured [8] resulting in much higher void content for the glassfibre mat with sizing. Also in this case the wetting results follows the previous quality check of the composite, Fig. 6. For the fourth case no visible difference in wetting was observed, Fig. 8. These fibres have shown big difference in strength after hot-wet treatment and it seems likely that the DAT cannot foresee such differences. However out of four cases wetting measurements with the DAT follows the properties of the composite in three cases.

One main advantage with the DAT is that it measures wettability on real reinforcements but still on the fibre bundle scale. Another is that it measures the wetting perpendicular to the fibres which often is the case in real production. None of the methods described in the introduction has these features. The system has however some flaws. The equipment only measures the drop from one side which is be troublesome for anisotropic reinforcements. There is also a limit in viscosity for the experimentally used liquid and the surface of the solid has to be plane. Furthermore, although it was not observed during this test series, evaporation of resin chemicals and the structure of the reinforcement may increase the scatter of the results.

To conclude, the experiments have shown that it is possible to measure wetting between resin and real reinforcements with the dynamic contact angle measurement unit FIBRO DAT. The measured values appear to have a strong correlation with the mechanical properties of the finished composite.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors express their sincere gratitude to, Prof. Rikard Gebart at SICOMP, Prof. Håkan Gustafsson, Dr. Allan Holmgren and Dr. Mats Ericsson at the University of Technology in Luleå, Ove Lindström and Eva Skoglund at ASSI Tech Center in Piteå, Rainer Bergström at Ahlström in Mikkeli, Finland and finally Stina Gerdes and Jan Elftonson at the Institute of surface energy in Stockholm.

7. REFERENCES

1. Hiemenz, P.C., "Surface Tension and Contact Angle", *Principles of Colloid and Surface Chemistry*, pp. 287-289
2. Kamath, Y.K., Dansizer, C.J., Hornby, S., Weigmann, H.D., "Surface Wettability Scanning of Long Filaments by a Liquid Membrane Method", *Textile Research Institute*, **57**, pp. 205-213, (1987)
3. Wagner, H.D., "Spreading of liquids on cylindrical surfaces: Accurate determinatic of contact angle", *Journal of Applied Physics*, **67**, pp. 1352-1355 (1990)
4. Chwastiak, S., "A Wicking Method for Measuring Wetting Properties of Carbon Yarns", *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, **42**, pp. 298-309, (1972)
5. ISO/TR 3717-1975
6. Berg, J.C., *Wettability*, Marcel Dekker (1993)
7. Dahlbäck, L.M., "Wetting Between Resin and Reinforcement in fibre Composites", SICOMP Technical Report 94-001, SICOMP, Box 271, 94126 Piteå, Sweden (1994)
8. Lundström, T.S., Gebart, B.R., "Influence From Process Parameters on Void Formation in Resin Transfer Moulding", *Polymer Composites*, **15**, No 1, (1994)